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Study of Habitat and Foraging Behaviour in Grey francolin (*Francolinus pondicerianus*) in Shekhawati Region of Rajasthan, India

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Abstract

Grey francolin (*francolinus pondicerianus*) is widely distributed bird in India except in high Himalaya and in north east.

Shekhawati region of Rajasthan is the north east part of Rajasthan and has 30, 490 km² total geographical area and most of area Semiarid zone. Grey francolin can seen in groups or pair or solely during morning and evening for foraging. Preferred habitat of grey francolin is bushy area, agricultural boundaries, land boundries and sand dunes with Bushes. Seansonal variations in population dencity of this bird mainly due to availability of food. Poaching of grey francolin mainly for it meat results in declins of its population.

Keywords

Grey Francolins, Shekhawati Region, Variation in Population, Habitat Preference.

Introduction

Birds are bipedal, feathered and warm blooded animals. The Indian subcontinent has about 13% of the world's avian species, 1340 bird species reported from India (**Ali and Ripley 1987**).

Rajasthan is the largest state, located in the north western part of India and Shekhawati region of Rajasthan located in the North-western part, in **Transitional plains of inland drainage** climatic zone of state with average rain fall of 300-400 mm. The fauna of this area are includes various orders of avifauna, out of which order galliformes includes heavy bodies ground feeding birds and this order includes shout 290 species.

Grey francolins (*francolinus pondicerianus*) is the member of family phasianidae of order galliformes, its local name is **Teetur** or **Bhoora**. It is larger than quails with stronger bills and feet. It is ground nesting omnivorous and non-migratory bird, shows worldwide distribution except Sahara desert, the arctic and colder area (**fuller etal. 2000**), in India it shows wide distribution except in high Himalaya and in north-east (**India biodiversity portal 2021**), francolins is small game bird which inhabited in open cultivated area as well as scrub forest. It is highly sedentary bird, seldom moving far from where they hatch. When disturbed it prefers to run instead of fly but will fly short distance if necessary. Francolins are gregarious and are diurnal but usually forage at dawn and dusk. It has average size 30-35 cm, with grey neck and chest feathers and rusty red head. It has short round wing and small bill, Wings and tail feathers are brown, rust whitening grey. Both sexes are almost similar but males are larger than females having dark brown U shaped patch on their belly and sharp spur (**Islam 1999**). Diet of this birds mostly seeds, from wide variety of plants such as grasses, seeds, leaves and insects (termites and ants), insect eggs and their larvae. It said to be omnivorous nature (**hussain etal. 2012**).

Monogamous grey francolins forms pair before the breeding season. Nesting occurs mostly in spring, eggs are laid in march-april, however a few pairs also nest in September and October after monsoon (**Roberts1991**). Both parents attend the young chicks after hatching (**Roberts1991**).

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Population decline of grey francolin has been well documented due to habitat destruction and increased use of pesticides (Roberts 1991). Grey francolin has under gone an overall 79% decline in last a decade but is listed as least concern in IUCN red list (IUCN 2015) due to its wide distribution range, only a few research study have been carried out in Rajasthan and no research have been carried out in Shekhawati. So there is need to study with specific objective of gathering information on (1) Ecology (2) Breeding behavior (3) Nest structure (4) Clutch size (5) Incubation period and (6) hatching success of grey francolin in the natural habitat in Shekhawati region of Rajasthan.

Objective of study

Grey francolin is a omnivorous and it also play a role of biological controller in nature, the occurrence, ecology and ethology of this bird is not studied vastly in Shekhawati region so proposed research work will increase knowledge about the status of this bird in Shekhawati region.

Grey francolin is a popular game bird and decline in population of this bird has well documented but it is listed as least concern in red data of IUCN due to its wide distribution, insufficient data exist about its population decline. There may several reasons for this population decline as habitat loss, Indiscriminate hunting by human for it meat, predation and indiscriminate use of pesticide in this area in cultivation / agricultural land. All these reasons will be studied and observation and conclusion will help us to understand about the species and its conservational strategies.

Review of Literature

The estimation about total no. of birds have been made by Mayer (1946), he estimated total 8600 bird species in world, according to him there are 146 families and 230 orders. Presently 8600-9016 species are found in world (anon 2004). Indian subcontinent contains 1300 species of birds which is the 13% of total species (Grimmette 1998), 48 birds families are present in subcontinent. According to Ali and Repely (1987) 176 species of birds are endemic (local) to the Indian subcontinent according to Grimmett (1998) Indian peninsula is the home of many bird families. Ali. S. (1945) observed ecology and ethology of grey francolins. Bump and Bump (1964) made study and review about grey and black francolins Choudhry and Bhatti (1992) studied biology of grey francolins in central Punjab plains. Five species of francolins are reported from India India (Ali and Ripely 1983, Grimmette 2011; Rasmuesen and Andersion2012), Hilaluddin and Kaul. R (2007) observed reasons behind galliformes hunting.

Hussain I, Nisa and Khalil S (2012) observed population, ecology and ethology of grey francolins. Kalsi R S (2005) observed that habitat destruction and pesticide use impacts on population of grey francolins. Kalsi R S (2007) observed state, distribution and management of galliformes in arid and semi arid zones in India. Kalsi R.S. and Rana (2004)observed habitat prefers of breeding grey francolin in agricultural land scope. Khalil and Anwar M (2016) reported parameters about habitat preference in grey francolin. Devesh gadhvi (2020) observed seasonal variation in the grey francolins in habitat preference.

Rajasthan has 40% of the Indian avifauna. due to wide variety of habitats and geographical status state has 510species of birds (Grimmette and inskipp 2003) Devarshi (2004) reported total 496 bird species in state, which is about 40% of Indian avifauna (1254 species) In state 17 endemic species are present (Ali and Ripley 1987) The Shekhawati region is the north-eastern part of Rajasthan and has 30490 km² total geographical area3 districts namely Churu (31%), Jhunjhunu (29%) and Sikar (40%) shares this area and climatic conditions of this area is mostly semi arid. Variety of bird species founds in this region (Rahmani 1987), various efforts made by researcher to study about avi fauna that can be cited in following paragraphs. Ojha A. etal. (2008) observed data about ecology and conservation of Indian peafowl in Jhunjhunu district. Dubey-S. (2008) observed data about bird in sewage wetland of Jhunjhunu city. Sheoran (2009) reported total of 130 species belonging to 33 families and 15 orders in Jhunjhunu district. D. Keshar (2010) observed population data and ecology about indian peafowl in Shekhawati region. Singh S. etal. (2015) observed parakeet diversity and its impact on ber (*Ziziphus moritiana*). They also made study about reproductive behavior of rose ringed parakeet (*Psittacula krameri*) Singh S. etal. (2020) observed a good growth in the number of peafowl in Shekhawati region of Rajasthan.Dadhich (2024) studied general occurrence of grey francolins in Shekhawati region of Rajasthan.

Methodology The Study area included semiarid zone of Shekhawati region of Rajasthan, which located in the north western Rajasthan in transitional plains of inland drainage climatic zone of state. Geographical Extension of this region from 26°26" to 29° 20" N latitude and 74°44" to 76°34'E longitude on the map. This region includes whole of Jhunjhunu and Sikar district along with a small part of Churu and negligible part of Nagour districts.

The survey was conducted by random sampling method in which direct call of birds and sighting were recorded with the help of binocular, Nikon D7500 Game DSLR Camera and

voice recorder.

Data were also collected from local farmer, bird watcher and local tribal peoples popularly known as "Banbawaria", Inhabited near forest. Line transect method was applied for collection of population data.

Analysis

The collected datas were analysed and general assumption were made, which can be described as follows

(1) Habitat Study :**(A) Preferred Habitat**

Majority of grey francoline observed in bushy area, Agricultural land boundaries and sand dunes with bushes. The preferred habitat helps in protection from predators as they can run and hide themselves in these area. The grey colour of grey francoline is similar to surrounding area so bird can Comouflage themselves with surrounding back grounds to Escape predation and hunting. on the basis of data collected from agricultural lands as well as from scurb forest suggest that number of grey francolin are more numerous than scurb forest probably due to more availability of food in agricultural lands because during summer these numbers declines due to scarcity of food. Grasses and bushes provides facility to build their nests, grasses and bushes convers their nests from predators and temperature variations.

Fig. 1 – Hided male under shrubs

Fig. 2 – Group of Grey francolins in grassland area

(B) Roosting Behaviour:

Roosting in birds define as rest or sleep usually at night in a safe place. Safety parameters are protection from predators and changing environmental factors.

Roosting in grey francolins in shekhawati region of rajasthan can be described as follows

(i) Roosting place: As shekhawati region is the semi arid zone,most of vegetation includes small trees, shrubs and bushes.Grey francolins prefers these vegetation, they also roosts on ground in grassland area. Group of grey francolin can be seen on khejri tree so they can escape from predators During roosting grey francolins perchs in group and remains connected with each other.

(ii) Roosting time: Roosting time is before sunset and they leave roosting before sunrise. Average time of roosting is 8 to 10 hours according to season.

(iii) Roosting strategy:Grey francolin roost in group or in pairs. Mothers roosts with their chicks.

Fig. 3 – Roosting group of Grey francolins in noon

Fig. 4 – Roosting group of Grey francolins under *Khejri* tree

Fig. 5 – Roosting group of chicks of Grey francolin.

(2) Foraging Behaviour:**(A) Diet Composition**

Grey francolin is omnivorous in nature it diet includes creals, seeds from wide variety of plants ,grit,insects, insect eggs and their larvae.Habitat prefered by bird fulfillls dietary requirement also. Since semiarid area are rich in succulant plants so bird can fulfill their requirment of food as well as water also.

(B) Foraging Time: Maximum foraging activities can be seen during morning and evening.....

(C) Foraging strategy

They forages in groups. or solely or in pairs. During foraging they walks actively and restricted their movements in area rich of crops, weeds, graine and seeds. Generally grey francolin forages separately from other bird species.

(D) Interaction with others

No fighting were observed with own species members during Foraging. Chicks are active feeders and forages in group with or without their parents. During noon no activity can be seen, they hides in bushes or rest under shrubs.

Fig. 6 – Male searching for food

Fig. 7 – Foraging behaviour

(E) Seasonal Fluctuations in Foraging Population : Due to shy nature of to grey francolin it rarely se Can not, seen easily, grey color of body is similar to surrounding enviroment 80 it is deficult to observe this bird easily. Make so in this circumstances Calling of this bird is key feature to observe it preference.

Calling of this bird are of two types mainly "Teu - Teu - Tea" and "Patila - Patila - Patila" On the basis of data of recorded calling and direct observation it is assumed that the grey francolin Show Seasonal variations in its population.

In march-april and post monsoon season maximum population density can seen.

This seasonal variation is due to availability of food water and shelter

March-april and post monsoon season is breeding season of grey francolin this also impacts on seasonal variation of densit of population

(F) Foraging Behaviour in Chicks- Chicks are dark grey in colour and feeds actively in grasses area. A female with chicks can seen easily during foraging –

Fig. 8 – Foraging activity of chicks of Grey francolins

Conclusion

on the basis of various data collected it can be assumed that grey francolin present in large numbers in Shekhawati region because this area is semi arid in nature, unique geographical structure with grasses, bushes and sand dunes provides shelter and wide variety of Grasses and bushes increases in size during monsoon and availability of food also increases during this season. Both of these two things affects the numbers of grey francolin. Increased grasses and bushes provides shelter from predators and provides space for nest building and increased food reduces competition among conspecific members. Following three factors affects population of grey francolin:

1. Destruction of habitat
2. Hunting for meat . they can fly less so are poached easily
3. Increased use of pesticides also responsible for declining the number of grey francolin,as these chemicals enters the body through seeds and insects they eat.However more investigation is needed.

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